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Research Article

**AN ASSESSMENT OF FREQUENCY AND PERCENTAGE OF
DANGEROUS CAUSES, DEMOGRAPHIC FEATURES AND
INHERITED FETAL DEFORMITIES****¹Dr. Sidra Baig, ¹Dr. Iqra Khan, ²Dr. Wajeeha Fayyaz**¹WMO DHQ Hospital Kasur²WMO DHQ Hospital Okara**Abstract:**

Objective: They recognize inborn irregularity or their dangerous feature at expecting female showing in a community segment sanatorium.

Methods: Their annoyed part study is conduct on their section of Obstetrics at Allied Hospital, Faisalabad from September 2016 to August 2017. Expediency example is worn on the learn. Every person female who's obtainable by analyze inborn anomaly successively moreover on off suffering person section and come straight to region form their extinction for pregnancy be incorporated later than the learned spoken or printed approval. A predesigned preformed is worn on get a whole the past, linked danger factor or appropriate in sequence for their inborn anomaly. They facts is analyze quantitatively for with SPSS.

Results: The entire on 11,946 females are admitting on Obstetrics section through their learning phase. Information is intended in every day foundation since off suffering person' or on suffering person' report for the sanatorium. There information is analyzing for by means of evocative sign; occurrence allocation method. Elsewhere whole 87 (0.73%) shows among dissimilar killing inborn anomaly. surrounded by him, 34 (39.1%) are gents, 47 (54.1%) are women's or 6 (7.4%) for their fetuses among sexual category can't not apparent. All their female who deliver offspring through inborn anomalies, where not attractive folic acid through pregnancy 49 (56.4%). motherly era limitation exposed these elsewhere for 87 females, 37 (42.1%) are connecting their era on 26-30 years. bulk on suffering person related and unfortunate socioeconomic rank example: 71 (81.5%). inborn anomaly obtainable further on fetuses for assorted females then it folks among initial pregnancy. The bulk commonly concerned body scheme where middle anxious scheme 45 (51.6%) follow on musculoskeletal 16 (18.4%), gastrointestinal organization 15 (17.3%), inborn syndrome 7 (8.0%), genitourinary 2 (2.5%), cardiac 1 (1.2%) and respiratory system 1 (1.2%). termination: Their middle anxious organization is pretentious has mainly. Healthcare establishment should think main avoidance on the appearance for immunization such since Rubella injection, nourishment or medicine such since folic acid near shrink avoidable inborn anomaly. They spirit extra assist on rising consciousness between females.

Keywords: inborn anomaly, fetuses, Pakistan, occurrence, danger factor.

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INTRODUCTION

Universal, inborn irregularity in a worldwide fitness matter or show main function of prenatal death or morbidity, oars healthy in infancy expire, constant sickness or disability [1]. Some study has informed to mainly household wellbeing be concerned organization or still society stand extended living unwell fitness belongings owing of inborn irregularity opinion of Parma ret al, 66% on inborn anomaly were for unidentified etiology. Inborn irregularity and delivery defect be able to describe its structural and useful irregularity counting metabolic disease, where be in attendance in the occasion on delivery. Various study contain established has third to eight weeks for development were their mainly significant era form the growth of parts or some change through his era cause deformity They occurrence on inborn variance change in dissimilar nation. Conversely, its variety among three to seven%. It has predictable had 276,000 newborn deaths happen yearly owed to inborn anomaly internationally. They have speculated to 20 -30% newborn death along with 30-50% passing away later than neonatal era happens suitable of inborn imperfection. Inside the United Kingdom it predictable figures in inborn irregularity for 15, 966 is evidence. World health organization (WHO) had predictable in our country 26,627 and 2.07% passing away happen owing of inborn fault on 2011 or they had improved by 2.35% in an annual [2]. There mainly widespread inborn anomaly description on learning is heart imperfection go after and facial, fissure edge, Down syndrome or neural tube imperfection. a further learning on Malhotra or Thapar11, show that their mainly ordinary irregularity is connected on gastrointestinal area pursue on the anxious method. Conversely, some further learn description neural tube imperfection is their mainly recurrent irregularity [3].

Their etiological danger issue form inborn deformity comprises hereditary or ecological issue, era of a mother, socioeconomic rank, motherly contact with teratogen, emission, motherly sickness, smoke or alcohol utilization is fine as consanguinity3-5. It's proved too obvious has inborn imperfection happen further on small labor heaviness or consanguineous wedding, 5, 19. At accumulation, learning contain description to inborn irregularity were further ordinary in gents' fetuses or in mature mothers [4]. Furthermore, require of foliate supplementation, smoke or alcohol utilization are as well mainly ordinary danger issue for inborn irregularity [5]. Their community wellbeing basis after this learning is for verifies their major danger issue on fetal inborn irregularity they determination assist in

accomplishment for effectual interference on anticipation of inborn irregularity. There purpose on that learning is of recognize their mainly usually see inborn imperfection in expecting female on a community segment, they source or their major danger issue that resolve more assist in rising consciousness between females.

PATIENTS AND METHODS:

Their annoyed part study is conduct on their section of Obstetrics at Allied Hospital, Faisalabad from September 2016 to August 2017. There organization moral support is firstly full. Thier whole for 11,946 females are included in Obstetrics section including their learning phase of that hundred has inborn irregularity. Nevertheless, one hundred surveys matter, just 87 are suitable or 13 disqualified since these suffering people are distribute exterior learning system. Successive expediency example is worn form their function of a learning. Every female whose accessible by recognize inborn irregularity also in off suffering people section and come straight near form the extinction for pregnancy are incorporated later than they learned unwritten permission.

These females whose stay off suffering people section has known assent form study or questionnaire are crammed but can't convey on learning system are disqualified from learning. The predesigned Performa is worn be get a whole record of a female for discovers elsewhere their connected danger issue of inborn irregularity. Their changeable incorporated were given in board 2 or 3. Later than record or assessment, deliverance is behavior opinion of the typical set of rules follow in delivery area. Every one pertinent data for the irregularity is recognized of a Performa. Karyotyping is not achieved owing on non-affordability. Their information is examined quantitatively with SPSS report 20. Evocative figures are tabularizing in their appearance of occurrence through fraction.

RESULTS:

Their whole of 11,946 female confesses on Obstetrics section through their learning phase. Facts are planned in each day base since off suffering people or its suffering people proceedings of sanatorium. There information is inspection for use expressive figures; occurrence allocation method. Elsewhere in whole 87 (0.73%) obtainable by dissimilar inborn irregularity fetuses. amongst then, 34 fetuses are gents (39.0%), 47 (54.0%) are women's fetuses or 6 (7.3%) contain no obvious sexual category recognition. along with the entire, bulk of a fetuses are with heaviness >600 gm example. 34 (39.1%), board 1. concerning gestational era, bulk of fetuses

are born among third trimester 26-30 weeks 24 (29.3%) 11 (13.3%) involving 31-35 weeks or 10 (12.16%) are further then 35 weeks follow it second trimester 21 to 25 weeks 22 (26.7%) or 17 (19.6%) few then 20 weeks. motherly era limit exposed to elsewhere for 87 female 37 (42.3%) are among 26-30 years board 1. inborn irregularity accessible further of fetuses in varied female, persons contain five and further kids 27(31.1%) then persons among earliest pregnancy 14 (17.0) (board 1). Consanguinity is not thus elevated on their learning 35 (40.3%) combine, relations record for inborn irregularity is optimistic on 21 (24.2%). Major figure for female 67 (78.3%) has rejection earlier pretentious kid. just 19 (23.2%) for females give a record and contain a kid through inborn irregularity. Record of folic acid ingestion is optimistic just in 38 (46.4%) even as bulk 44 (53.5%)

are not captivating folic acid in pregnancy. Bulk of suffering people are unfortunate 71 (81.5%) charge on their profession or profits. Just 12 (13.6%) females are bare by disease similar to chicken pox, measles or syphilis its initial trimester illness. Another way give, huge figure 75 (86.3%) in female has no record for such disease on initial trimester. Mother among RH positive blood collection has further inborn irregularity 74 (85.1%) then these of RH negative board 2. The majority frequently occupied organization scheme be middle anxious organization 45 (51.6 %) pursue on musculoskeletal 16 (18.4%), gastrointestinal classification 15 (17.3%), inborn syndromes 2 (2.5%), genitourinary 2 (2.4%), cardiac 1 (1.2%) or respiratory classification 1 (1.2%), board 3.

Table – I: Demographics

Parameter		Frequency	Percentage
Parity	G - I	15	17.3
	G - II	22	25.1
	G - III to G - IV	23	26.3
	> G5	27	35.6
	Total	87	100
Maternal Age (Years)	< 20	4	4.6
	20 - 25	14	16
	26 - 30	37	42.6
	31 - 35	26	29.7
	> 35	6	6.7
	Total	87	100
Gestational Age (Weeks)	< 20	17	19.6
	21 - 25	22	25.3
	26 - 30	24	27.4
	31 - 35	13	14.8
	> 35	11	12.7
	Total	87	100
Birth Weight (grams)	400	16	18.4
	400 - 500	14	16.1
	500 - 600	23	26.5
	> 600	24	39.1
	Total	87	100
Baby's Gender	Male	34	39
	Female	47	54
	Not Clear	6	6.8
	Total	87	100

Table – II: Danger Causes

Parameter		Frequency	Percentage
Maternal Blood Group	O+	27	32.8
	O-	2	2.3
	A+	26	29.7
	A-	3	3.5
	B+	18	21.8
	B-	5	6
	AB+	3	3.5
	AB-	3	2.5
	Total	87	100
Consanguinity	Yes	35	40.3
	No	52	63.5
	Total	87	100
Previous Infected Child	Yes	19	23.2
	No	68	78.2
	Total	87	100
Family History	Yes	21	24.2
	No	66	75.9
	Total	87	100
H/O Folic Acid Intake	Yes	38	46.5
	No	49	56.4
	Total	87	100
Socioeconomic Status	Poor	71	81.5
	Average	16	19.6
	Total	87	100

Table – III: Circulation of Inborn Deformity

System and Malformation		Frequency	Percentage
CNS	Hydrocephalus	22	26.7
	Anencephaly	18	20.7
	Meningocele	3	3.5
	Agensis of Corpus Colossus	1	1.3
	Encephalocele	1	1.5
Musculoskeletal	Tulips	3	3.5
	Spine Bifida	7	8.1
	Achondroplasia	1	1.3
	Skeletal Dysplasia	5	6
Genitourinary	Posterior Urethral Value	1	1.2
	Hydronephrosis	1	1.2
Digestive	Omphalocele	2	2.4
	Imperforate anus	1	1.4
	Fetal as cites	5	6.1
	Esophageal Artesia	1	1.5
	Duodenal Artesia	1	1.2
Congenital Syndromes	Cleft lip	5	6.2
	Arnold Chari malformation	1	1.2
	Dandy walker syndrome	1	1.2
	Hydro fetalis	5	6

DISCUSSION:

Inborn irregularity shows an important position in prenatal death or morbidity, is healthy as babyhood passing away, constant sickness or disability¹, 2. They are detailing the majority household wellbeing classification or still culture stand ultimate unwell healthiness belongings owing on inborn irregularity. The whole in 87 females obtainable by inborn irregularity is observe through their learning era. Consequently, incidence for inborn irregularity of our learning is 0.73%. It communicates with their learning in Liaquat Memorial Hospital Kohat²⁴ of 0.96%? With another give learning for Bangalore or Egypt description on elevated occurrence 14.26% or 9.8% correspondingly,²⁵. Their difference of facts as of dissimilar location might live suitable to exact danger factor similar to civilization, environmental allocation, or consanguinity, socioeconomic position, educational or dietary issue [6].

We are learning, inborn irregularity is established further in women's fetuses then gents' fetuses (54.0% women's or 39.0% gents). It might exist since current learning does not symbolize their entire inhabitants. Alike on their Gull, Jabeen or Khan's learning. On difference, figure on learning have reported male fetuses among inborn irregularity are further then women's fetuses [7].

The signify mass recommended it mainly fetuses' mass in usual of relative in gestational era (board 1). Current learning does not discover connection of delivery mass through innate imperfection. We termination were reliable by their conclusion in the learning complete on Civil Hospital Karachi [5]. These are astonishing is more than a few learn description connection linking delivery mass or inborn irregularity [8]. Era in the mother linked

through inborn irregularity was measured significant issue. Motherly limit of our learning obtainable inborn irregularity further ordinary on era among 26 or 30 years (43.8%), which as alike among learning perform India¹⁸. Our difference learning as well description that aged mothers and era better than 30 has eminent occurrence form produce inborn deformed offspring [9]. While on the learning just 3.7% female by era further then 35 years are establish by inborn deformed fetuses. Its might be since figure on female of era collection few then 35 years be the minority, therefore is a prejudice of our learning plan [10]. While, his learning proposes to female current by inborn irregularity of our system in during further danger issue mainly in their mothers of our learning belong on reduced or era could not be there for causative feature of inborn irregularity in those females.

We establish further inborn irregularity of fetuses for diverse female having this reliable by their previous domino effect. There elevated regularity (board 1) designate with the aim of their inborn irregularity might boost as their delivery categorize add to. Hence, it appears to diverse female were they perfect aim collection for defensive determine or community wellbeing learning movement.

Even though we learning establish that important figure in female (board 2) fit in with RH positive blood collection. They can't discover some specific clarification of these.

In our explanation of huge that consanguineous wedding had shut involvement through inborn irregularity [13] since of a homozygous appearance for recessive genes present at birth of blood relatives (first cousin wedding). Nevertheless, domino effect recognized opposing conclusion 63.5% of female has

non-consanguineous wedding, having this is agreement through previously learn complete in Aga Khan University Hospital, Karachi [14]. Therefore, this sequence gives position of extra investigation of these regions. According of our knowledge conclusion 23.1% female has record for earlier exaggerated kid. There is extra hold through their disobedience of nutrients particularly folic acid ingestion, combined or unfortunate socioeconomic rank in a learning collection. Folic acid lack is recognized danger aspect for containing infant among neural tube imperfection. We learning 46.4 % of female are disobedient of folic acid ingestion throughout premature pregnancy. we accumulation, that our learning about central nervous system is their mainly exaggerated organization 26.9 % hydrocephalus, 20.0 % anencephaly or 8.0% reason for spine bifida optional tough connection through folic acid lacking. These recommended more require for execution of civilizing fast in female mainly folic acid ingestion.

The majority of mother of our learning fit in with reduced socioeconomic category. These might be individual of because form elevated occurrence for inborn irregularity within our location. These conclusions were reliable among their judgment of learning complete at Karachi Civil hospital by Raza MZ ET al5. Relative's record for inborn deformity is 24.2 percent of our learning or bulk 75.7% female has no relative's record. Which is additional? Reliable by among learning judgment of non-consanguineous wedding 63.5%. Conclusions were alike with learning complete in Kharian, Pakistan is simply 22.2% are by consanguineous wedding. Their knowledge about learning is mainly ordinary exaggerated classification is their Central Nervous System pursue via musculoskeletal or than Gastro Intestinal Track. These are moreover hold with further investigated Hussein's ET al3. Now adding, numerous extra learning contain description by Central Nervous System is their mainly exaggerated organization such as their learning for UK15, Egypt20, India2,17, or Pakistan12. Our difference, in learning with Butt et al description of the mainly ordinary inborn irregularity is heart imperfection go after by and facial, cleft lip, down syndrome or Central Nervous System imperfection. A further learning establishes gastrointestinal connected imperfection where further ordinary pursues with Central Nervous System imperfection. Alike, in learning from India description musculoskeletal associated irregularity is mainly widespread pursue with Central Nervous System22. Their boundaries for our learning are as to it is minor worry sanatorium learning hence this was not envoy for the society at

huge. Now totaling, interference similar to serum Alfa-fetoprotein, acetyl cholinesterase, amniocentesis, karyotyping was not obtainable at minor worry sanatorium middle form premature analysis of inborn deformity. These are suggested to healthcare responsiveness movement must be obtainable at every community segment sanatorium, prenatal or antenatal lessons must be obtainable of every community fitness segment, responsiveness concerning folic acid ingestion through female prenatal or antenatal appointment must be their region for deliberation or administration must ease prenatal showing experiment at community fitness inside.

CONCLUSION:

Inborn irregularities were recurrent of our location or Central Nervous System is their mainly usually exaggerated organization. Women sexual category, combined, unfortunate socioeconomic rank, folic acid ingestion is connected danger issue information of incidence or linked danger cause of inborn irregularity were significant to arrangement defensive procedures at dissimilar intensity by healthcare specialized.

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